

PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS: PROACTIVE APPROACH TO COMBAT FRAUD AND CYBER ATTACKS

¹Shailaj Kumar Shrivastava and ²Amitesh Kumar

¹Principal, A.M. College, Gaya, Bihar, India

² Guest Faculty, College of Commerce Arts & Science, Patna.

Abstract:

In ever-increasing era of digital world, all transactions of corporate, enterprise and governance goes digital. The execution of transactions are easier, efficient, timely, correctly and user friendly. There are wide variety of associated threats and vulnerability with it. These threats may be internal or external. One of the biggest and high cost threats is 'Fraud'. Fraudulent activities have ability that can compromise integrity of organization and at the same time may cripple organizations bottom-line. As the volume of data increases, the possible and potential cause of attacks and frauds increases simultaneously or subsequently. It will not be easier to find and point out the fraudulent activities and risks at the time of its occurrence. The fraudulent activities are not just simple task and can't be traced out by using simple methodologies and regressive or explanatory methods. Everyday a new threat comes in picture, so there is urgent need to take proactive measures to control it. Instead of summarize and visualize the threat, one should become more vigilant, active, sensitive and predictive to prevent the potential fraud before it takes place. Predictive Analytics is a better approach to deal with it.

Keywords: Predictive analytics, models, frauds, cyber attacks, fraudulent activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

Predictive Analytics means to trace the fraud, its pattern and future behavior before it happens. Predictive analytics allows system/organization to become proactive. The proactive measures eliminate the problems before they have chance to appear. Predictive modeling, data mining, machine learning, quantum computing and artificial intelligence are used to predict, detect and identify suspects of unknown future events [1-5]. The strength of Predictive Analytics is to make illusions to knowledge base, which is its core power. The tremendous growth in use of wide range of applications on public networks (The Internet) makes a serious cause of frauds and cyber attacks. Internal factors are also there. Fraudulent activities and attacks may be a normal transaction, hidden or associated with some other transactions. By using technologies and methods helps the system/organization to detect the orientation and patterns of data using data models. This will help the system to find the unusual behavior and wrong transactions. This will helps to find the fraud and attacks before it takes place. The proactive nature of system strengthens the organization and helps in increasing their profitability and loyalty to their customers.

II. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND:

Predictive Analytics helps us to connect to data effective action by drawing reliable conclusions about the current conditions and future events. Enabling business to use predictive models exploits patterns found in historical data to identify potential risks and opportunities before they occur. Predictive analytics can use all available data. The 360° (degree) problem view approach will help the model to find and point out every pattern of data and their connections with each other. The four corner data are

- Interaction data (Emails, chats, notes, etc.)
- Attitudinal data (opinions, preferences, social media, survey, etc.)
- Descriptive data (attributes, demographics, characteristics, etc.)
- Behavioral data (payment history, usage history, login history, etc.)

III. THE PREDICTIVE THREATS & FRAUD ANALYSIS MODEL:

1. Continuous Observation and Tracking of Environment:

This stage of model simply collects data from various sources like, excel sheets, relational Database, SQL, Big Data, etc. Data are in different forms and nature. Some data are in rest mode and some are in motion. Most of the data may be unstructured or structured in nature. On this basis following activities takes place.

- Leaks identification
- Help to increase compliances
- Close eyes on influential activities in critical business functions

2. Detection of Suspicious Activities:

The second part of the model helps to make prediction on the basis of suspicious activities. In this case the prediction is based on Data mining (Structured), Text mining (unstructured) and statistical analysis by using sophisticated algorithms. Following activities are traced.

- Fraudulent data patterns identification.
- Reduce false positives.
- Identification of sudden, unexpected, unforeseen, unlooked-for transaction patterns.
- Conniving, tricky, collusive and fraud merchants, employee and stakeholder's identification.

3. Control and Outcome:

For gain insights from predication process, it is necessary to act on those insights and findings. At this stage, deployment of these findings in algorithm and tools includes.

- Act in real-time environment to prevent abuse
- Reduce claims handling time
- Alert client and stakeholder of transaction frauds.

IV. PREDICTIVE ANALYTICS BENEFITS AND LIMITATIONS:

Binding of predictive analysis processes within the fraud detection system is important and vital, accompanied by various benefits and limitations as follows.

Benefits:

- Improving quality of data
- Fraud detection in real time
- Will find answers, in real time, to a series of questions regarding fraud issues
- Automatic data collection
- Operates with both structured and unstructured data
- Eliminates redundancy
- Increases efficiency in fraud detection
- Will help in reduce fraudulent claims
- High productivity

Limitations:

- High cost
- Unstructured data are not introduced to database
- Human hand is always needed, as it is automated tool

V. CONCLUSIONS

Fraud prevention is not a simple and easy task. It involves summarizing and visualizing of data from different source that comes in different formats by applying data/text mining and data filtering. It means it is a complicated and costly process. The intention is to encourage the safety from attacks, antifraud and makes the system proactive in nature. It improves the systems fraud prevention and detection capabilities. Sometime Big frauds results in organization bankruptcy or loss of their customers. Fraud Prevention gives direct benefit to the organization to make more profit as the customer's loyalty improves on the system.

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